

Youth, Culture & Sports

March 2026

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development, building on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the fourth round of data collection in 2025 and at the beginning of 2026, in comparison to the data collected in the previous third monitoring round.

In terms of Youth, Culture & Sports, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Youth with above basic overall digital skills” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Note
Data for Kosovo* not available. Data for North Macedonia for 2023 not available.

Source
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/isoc_sk_dskl_i21_custom_14882522/default/table?lang=en&page=time:2023 (accessed 10 November 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Ministerial Meeting on Culture

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Integration and stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives		Cultural cooperation initiatives	Regional cooperation and people-to-people exchanges	
	Participation in the Erasmus+ (E+) Programme	Support to Implementation of the EU acquis	Participation in the Culture Europe Programme	Participation in SHARE 2.0 initiative	European Week of Sport
Albania	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented	Increased number of Twinning projects	Increased number of projects under the Culture Europe Programme No updated information on the Culture Moves Europe initiative	Involved in the initiative / number of participating stakeholders not specified	Week of Sport organised Number of participants and partnering organisations not specified
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented	No Twinning projects reported	Increased number of projects under the Culture Europe Programme No updated information on the Culture Moves Europe initiative	Participation of 4 stakeholders	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
Kosovo	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented	No Twinning projects reported	Increased number of projects under the Culture Europe Programme No updated information on the Culture Moves Europe initiative	Involved in the initiative / number of participating stakeholders not specified	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
Montenegro	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented	No Twinning projects reported	Increased number of projects under the Culture Europe Programme Increased number of beneficiaries of individual mobilities in the Culture Moves Europe initiative/no residency host reported	Participation of 4 stakeholders	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
North Macedonia	Increased number of E+ projects and mobilities implemented	No Twinning projects reported	Increased number of projects under the Culture Europe Programme No updated information on the Culture Moves Europe initiative	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised with increased participation
Serbia	Increased number of projects and mobilities implemented	Increased number of Twinning projects	Increased number of projects under the Culture Europe Programme No updated information on the Culture Moves Europe initiative	No involvement in the initiative	Week of Sport organised with increased participation

Legend: On track or maintaining achievement | Moderately improving Challenges remain | Stagnating Significant challenges | Decreasing Major challenges | Information not available

Highlights

New Western Balkans Regional Skills Partnership established to promote cultural and creative industries by strengthening digital and green skills, fostering collaboration and supporting training and project development across the region
Successful implementation of the POLICY ANSWERS pilot measure supporting young innovators – the Western Balkans R&I Youth Awards and the R&I Youth Online Campaign, celebrating outstanding youth-focused success stories in R&I across the region

Strengthening Research and Innovation in the Western Balkans: The POLICY ANSWERS project

POLICY ANSWERS is a strategic initiative funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project “R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEStErN BalkanS”. The project focuses on enhancing research and innovation (R&I) policymaking and governance systems in the Western Balkans, while also addressing aspects of education, culture, youth, and sports. By providing essential support to the region’s development, POLICY ANSWERS plays a crucial role in strengthening the Western Balkans’ potential for successful participation in regional and multilateral research and innovation activities.

Partners

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